

Automated HITS to LASAR Translation

Application, Evaluation, Opportunities, and Obstacles

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Abstract— HITS (Hierarchical Integrated Test Simulator) and LASAR (Logic Automated Stimulus And Response) are two software platforms used for simulating digital circuits, determining their operation under specified faulty conditions, and judging the percentage of user-specified faults that are uniquely detected given a user-specified set of digital input patterns. These software platforms also generate files that may be imported onto automated test equipment (ATE) to allow the simulated input patterns to be applied to actual digital circuits and facilitate the detection of actual circuit faults. HITS is natively utilized on a variety of now-obsolete ATE systems and is, itself, obsolete. LASAR, on the other hand, is more technologically capable, manufacturer-supported, and utilized on myriad modern ATE systems. The need to migrate existing test application hardware and software from obsolete ATE systems that utilize HITS to supportable ATE systems that utilize LASAR presents the opportunity to simplify the migration effort by devising a method to automatically translate the simulation source data from HITS format into LASAR format.

This paper describes the development and evaluation of a software application that automatically translates HITS source data into LASAR source data with an emphasis on minimizing the need for manual intervention in the translation process. The similarities between HITS and LASAR source data formats allow for much of the HITS data to be faithfully translated; however some differences between the two present seemingly insurmountable obstacles that precipitate the need for manual translation efforts. These similarities and differences are described in detail. In addition, the translator application is evaluated according to three criteria: the total test duration for each translated simulation, the fault coverage attained for each translated simulation, and the estimated development cost savings realized through the use of the translator application. A sample of twelve existing LASAR simulations, for which the source data had been previously generated independently of existing HITS simulations for the same digital circuits, was used as a baseline to evaluate the performance of LASAR source data automatically translated from HITS source data.

The results indicate that the difference in total test duration between the existing and translated LASAR simulations is negligible, with an average difference of 7.96 ms for the sample set. The fault coverage rate attained, without further manual optimization, by the translated LASAR simulations varied widely with an average of 72% and one out of three attaining a fault

coverage rate above 95%, exceeding the organizational standard. Based on man-hour estimates of several individual LASAR simulation development tasks, utilizing the translator application was determined to reduce the development cost of LASAR simulations by 87%. Overall, the translator application was found to be an effective tool for translating HITS simulation source data into LASAR simulation source data.

Keywords— HITS; LASAR; translation; automated test equipment; rehost; digital circuit simulation; fault diagnostics; obsolescence; modernization; TPS

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper describes the development and evaluation of a software application that automatically translates Hierarchical Integrated Test Simulator (HITS) source data into Logic Automated Stimulus And Response (LASAR) source data, with an emphasis on minimizing the need for manual intervention in the translation process. The similarities and differences between the two are explored in detail, as well as the methodology employed to develop the translator application. The performance of the translator application is evaluated in terms of its impact on total digital testing duration, fault coverage, and organizational development cost versus development of simulation source data without automatic translation. Evaluation results are presented and conclusions are drawn which indicate that the translator application is an effective tool in the rehost of HITS simulation source data to a LASAR platform.

II. BACKGROUND

Within the Department of Defense (DoD), automated testing of digital circuitry at the circuit card level often employs a program specifically developed to model, simulate, and diagnose digital circuits and to simplify fault isolation. This program combines a user-defined, text-based model of the circuit with a user-defined set of digital input patterns to simulate the digital response of the circuit based on the model and input patterns, and to record a set of expected output patterns (one for each input pattern). Then the program considers a set of possible faults (often simply a node being “stuck at (logic) one” or “stuck at zero”) chosen by the user and known as the “fault universe”, and again simulates the

circuit response to determine another set of output patterns under these conditions. The output patterns associated with unique faults are compiled into a “fault dictionary”. The program also reports fault coverage – the percentage of faults in the fault universe that can be detected using the input patterns given [1]. The goal is to maximize fault coverage by applying an adequate set of digital input patterns.

After attaining an acceptable level of fault coverage, the input patterns and fault dictionary may be ported to an automated test system where they can be applied to actual test articles. This digital testing is often performed as an ancillary routine at some point during the execution of the main test program for a particular test article. If an input pattern produces an output that varies from the expected “good” result, the routine finds the corresponding “bad” output pattern for the given input pattern in the fault dictionary and reports to the user the circuit component or components most likely to be at fault.

Most automated test equipment (ATE) systems that utilize this type of digital circuit simulation and diagnostic software have a particular program with which they are compatible (and from which the fault dictionary and input pattern data can be imported to be translated into stimuli and diagnostic information for actual test articles). HITS and LASAR are two such simulation programs that are natively compatible with (among others) the Depot Automatic Test System for Avionics (DATSA) and the Versatile Depot Automatic Test Station (VDATS), respectively. Both HITS and the DATSA stations that utilize it are obsolete and increasingly difficult to support and maintain. Meanwhile, LASAR and the VDATS stations that utilize it are modern, reliable, supportable, and suitable replacements for HITS and DATSA.

An eminent effort to rehost a number of test programs from the DATSA to the VDATS will require rehosting any associated digital circuit simulation and diagnostic routines in order to maintain consistency in test capability and meet test coverage requirements. Successful efforts to devise an algorithm for automatically translating the native DATSA programming language Abbreviated Test Language for All Systems (ATLAS) common to many obsolescent automated test systems into the ANSI C language native to the VDATS and other modern automated systems [2] encourage the possibility of also devising an algorithm for automatically translating HITS circuit model, stimulus pattern, and fault universe source data into corresponding source data for LASAR simulations.

A number of similarities between HITS and LASAR exist which simplify efforts to automatically translate source data from one platform to the other. Foremost among these is the division of each platform into a series of similarly structured modules that accept particularly-formatted source data. The three basic types of source data that make up any digital circuit simulation are the model netlist, stimulus patterns, and fault universe.

The HITS model netlist (.mdl) file has three main sections – the preamble, the circuit component instantiation section, and the node interconnection section – along with certain other syntactically-required statements. The preamble includes

definitions of externally-defined components and descriptions of user-defined circuit components. User-defined components can be defined as MACROs (built using system-defined “primitives” – the building blocks of HITS digital logic – to define the structure of the component) or FUNCTIONALS (built using a more conventional programming language to describe the functionality of the component). The component instantiation section gives a name to each component on the circuit to be simulated and sets the type of each component. It also declares the names of circuit input and output pins. Finally, the node interconnection section defines how component pins are connected to each other and to input and output pins.

The HITS stimulus pattern batch (.bat) file is actually a sequence of captured commands executed at the operating system’s command prompt. It includes commands leading up to and including the execution of the HITS TESTSIM executive (which is actually meant to accept stimulus data input in real-time, one pattern at a time). At that point, a variety of commands for issuing patterns to the simulated circuit appear. Before pattern-generating commands are issued, the file may define a grouping of pins and give the group a name using the LIST command, or it may define a sequence of commands to be executed as a group using the MACRO command (not to be confused with a model netlist MACRO).

The HITS fault universe “predetect” (.det) file defines components or nodes to exclude from consideration as possible faults. The file contains a number of instances of the command “PREDETECT:” followed by the components and nodes to be excluded from consideration. Each excluded fault may also be specified as “stuck high” only or “stuck low” only with the commands “PREDETECT@1” and “PREDETECT@0,” respectively [3].

The LASAR model netlist is structured very similarly to the HITS model netlist. It also includes a component instantiation section and a node interconnection section. However, input and output pins are not declared in the instantiation section. Instead, labels are added in the interconnection section identifying them appropriately. In addition, custom components are not defined within the model netlist, but are instead defined in external files contained in an external component library (.lib) file that accompanies the other simulation files.

The LASAR stimulus pattern file also follows the general structure of the HITS pattern batch file, with one major difference. Whereas HITS simulation considers all nodal inputs to have settled to their respective logic levels before the output is handed off to subsequent components, LASAR allows for high-speed simulation that takes more detailed component timing information into consideration. One of the main advantages of LASAR is the ability to define timing “phases” for input pins and timing “windows” for output pins. HITS allows users to define the rate that patterns are issued in the Interface Test Adapter (ITA) description (.ita) file, but LASAR allows users to define the duration of patterns as well as the time at which certain inputs transition to the desired logic state (and, if applicable, return to a quiescent state) and the times between which certain output pins shall be sampled by the

ATE measurement device. The user can define multiple phases and windows for use with different groups of input pins and output pins, respectively. The timing information is contained within a “TSET” section of the stimulus pattern file.

The structure of the LASAR fault universe (or “faultlist”) file is somewhat similar to the HITS predetect file, particularly since each serves little purpose other than to identify faults to include or exclude from consideration. The LASAR faultlist, however, requires that some options are initialized, and all faults must be included or excluded explicitly. A typical LASAR fault list will include the statement “INSERT PRODUCTION FAULTS” which considers all possible faults for all nodes, and from there “EXCLUDE” statements are used to exclude individual faults from consideration or multiple faults when the statement “EXCLUDE FAULTLIST” is used (in conjunction with “ENDLIST”) [4].

The DATSA’s ATLAS test language was originally written from the perspective of testing analog circuitry, and digital testing and its demands were not facilitated as thoroughly. The ATLAS language, and therefore also the HITS programs specifically written for it, did not include a capability for utilizing bidirectional pins, so individual edge pins on the UUT can only be specified as primary input or primary output, but not both simultaneously. This disadvantage was typically compensated for by incorporating additional hardware, such as a tri-state buffer, into both the actual hardware (i.e. the ITA) and the simulation circuit model. On the other hand, LASAR includes functionality for bidirectional pins and also provides for simulation of open, or “High-Z”, logic state faults, whereas HITS only provides for simulation of “stuck at (logic) one” and “stuck at (logic) zero” faults [5]. Other differences between HITS and LASAR, such as fundamental syntax differences, differences in custom component definitions, and untranslatable stimulus pattern-generating commands, are discussed at length in the Methods section.

III. METHODS

A. Development

The translator application was programmed as a Windows form application in the C# language using Visual Studio 2010. The user friendliness associated with the graphical user interface of a Windows application was desirable, and because it is the only operating system allowed for use on prospective users’ primary computers, Windows was chosen as the application platform rather than LASAR’s native UNIX operating system.

The graphical user interface (GUI) for the HITS to LASAR translator application is depicted in Fig. 1. This is the primary view the user interacts with when using the application and it is shown in the figure after having performed the translation of a HITS model netlist (.mdl) file into a LASAR model netlist (.net) file. The placing of GUI components within the window is meant to reduce confusion. Resizing the window primarily expands the two text boxes that contain the source HITS and destination LASAR data to allow the user ample space for viewing the input and output data.

Fig. 1. Translator Application Screenshot

The behavior of the GUI buttons, with the exception of “clear all” depends upon the file type radio button that the user has selected. The “open” and “save” buttons launch familiar Windows file opening and saving dialogs, respectively, with file options defaulting to appropriate HITS and LASAR file types. After opening a HITS source data file of any type, the “convert” button calls one of three methods depending upon the current file type selection. The convertModel, convertPattern, and convertFaultlist methods constitute the majority of the functionality of the translator application. At the conclusion of each of the conversion methods, the LASAR text box is populated with the translated LASAR source data. The user can make changes to the HITS source data and rerun the conversion and can also make changes to the LASAR source data in the LASAR text box. When satisfied with the translation, the user may press the “save” button to save the LASAR source data to an appropriately-named LASAR file. Fig. 2 presents a high-level flow diagram for the translator application.

Though each conversion method is designed for a specific type of file, there are several similarities among them. Each uses an instance of the StringBuilder class to generate translated LASAR data. Each method first generates a header identifying the LASAR data as an automatically generated product of the translator application, along with other pertinent information. From there, individual lines of the HITS text box are read, one at a time, and parsed. Each conversion method makes extensive use of the regular expression (Regex) class to establish matches with acceptable forms of HITS syntax, and adds the appropriate translation for that HITS syntax to the StringBuilder instance. The first syntax that each conversion method seeks is HITS comment syntax. Whole-line comments are translated, and no further matches are sought. Mid-line comments are stripped and translated, and the remaining line is parsed for other HITS syntax. Each conversion method also searches for a comma at the end of the each line which, in HITS syntax, denotes that the subsequent line is a continuation of the current line. Such lines are combined until the aggregate line does not end with a comma, and are then parsed as a single line.

Fig. 2. Translator Application Program Flow Diagram

The `convertPattern` and `convertFaultlist` methods both generate an “open file” dialog and instruct the user to navigate to the associated HITS model netlist file. The methods then extract edge pin information from the model netlist and use it in different ways. The `convertPattern` method uses it to generate a pin grouping called HITSINPUTS. This is because HITS pattern commands can be executed upon the group INPUTS, which applies the pattern to all input pins. LASAR does not include this capability if the pattern is not uniform (i.e. all pins are set to the same state) and the order of the pins must be taken into account, so duplicating this implicit grouping in HITS with an explicit grouping in LASAR is necessary. The `convertFaultlist` uses the pin listing because edge pins are specified differently from other circuit nodes in fault inclusion or exclusion statements.

The syntax translated by the `convertModel` method is primarily component instantiation and node interconnection statements, in addition to syntax for other HITS statements that, for instance, denote the beginning or end of the model netlist, or sections thereof. Some HITS syntax has no LASAR

equivalent and is simply ignored. Component instantiation statements in HITS are of the form “(component type) = (component instantiations)” and multiple instantiations are separated by commas. The LASAR equivalent is simply transposed about the equals sign. HITS syntax requires that input and output pins are declared explicitly in a separate section. LASAR has no such requirement – rather, nodes are specified as “primary input” (PI), “primary output” (PO), or “bi-directional” (BI) within the node interconnect section. For this reason, the conversion method saves the HITS edge pins into lists and adds the appropriate PI or PO designation in the translation of the node interconnect section wherever an edge pin appears. Node interconnect statement syntax is nearly identical in HITS and LASAR, with only minor differences.

HITS model netlists may often include DEFINE, MACRO statements (DEFINE, FUNCTION or DEFINE, PRIMITIVE may also appear) prior to the component instantiation section. These statements, and a number of subsequent statements concluding with END, MACRO (or END, FUNCTIONAL or END, PRIMITIVE, as the case may be), define custom, user-generated components. LASAR includes functionality for

defining custom components, but the syntax is not included within the model netlist. Custom components in LASAR are defined in external files and use a substantially different syntax than HITS custom component definitions. Because of the elevated level of effort involved, and because this effort is wasted in cases where an equivalent component model already exists in the (more expansive) LASAR standard component library, these statements are not translated by the translator application. Instead, the LASAR data is appended with a message notifying the user that such statements must be manually translated. The HITS statements DECLARE, ROM; DECLARE, RAM; DECLARE, PLA; DECLARE DELAYLINE; DECLARE, MONO; and DECLARE, SSR appear alongside the component instantiation section, but are similarly not currently translated. Memory devices instantiated in such a way in HITS include all initial or static data specified inline, in the model netlist file. In LASAR, the data and other device specifications are included in a separate file, and the LASAR environment includes a form interface that simplifies building custom models and instantiations of these types of components. Future revisions of the translator application may include functionality to translate such DEFINE and DECLARE statements, but they are not currently supported.

The syntax translated by the convertPattern method is primarily stimulus pattern-generating commands, along with a variety of other, mostly incidental syntax. As described previously, the translator application automatically generates a generic timing specification for the simulation, which the user is encouraged to customize. Most pattern-generating commands include a command statement followed by an input pin name, a list of input names, or an input pin group name on which to apply the stimulus or stimuli.

A majority of commands (and abbreviations thereof) that appear in HITS stimulus pattern files have direct equivalent LASAR commands for which implementing the translation was fairly simple. These particular commands are summarized in Table 1. In most cases, the pattern-generating commands with LASAR equivalents are simply replaced, preserving the operands of the commands. However, there are several HITS commands for which there are no direct LASAR equivalents, and for which translation is far more complex.

TABLE I. EQUIVALENT HITS AND LASAR COMMANDS

HITS Command	LASAR Equivalent Command
CLEAR	LO
SET	HI
TOGGLE	CHANGE
HIZ	OFF
X	DONTCR
INCREMENT	BINARY
GRAY	GRAY
RANDOM	RANDOM
DRIVE	DRIVE
FOR I= 1 TO (X) DO / END	DO (X) / UNDO
MACRO	SUBROUTINE
APPLY	CALL
MASK	FUNK
UNMASK	RELEASE

The HITS pattern-generating commands BINARY, CIRCLE, DBINARY, DECREMENT, and SHIFT execute a variety of binary operations on groups of input pins, but do not have directly equivalent LASAR commands. Because of this, such functionality was added to the translator application through the use of LASAR subroutines. When one of these commands is encountered by the translator application, it first determines the number of affected pins. This information is then used by the Subroutine Generator class to automatically generate code for a subroutine that performs the operation corresponding to that particular HITS command. These automatically generated subroutines check the driving state of each pin and apply the stimulus required to achieve the same functionality as the HITS command being translated to each pin. If a user-defined pin group is specified as a parameter to one of these HITS commands, it is replaced by the corresponding list of individual pins. This is done since it is not possible to check the driving states of individual pins within a pin group using LASAR.

HITS pattern-generating commands may be conjoined using the AND operator, which signifies that the stimuli from the two commands is applied simultaneously. In LASAR, the semicolon (;) operator applies pattern stimuli at the conclusion of a pattern-generating command statement, and multiple stimulus patterns are buffered and applied simultaneously by omitting any intervening semicolons.

A MACRO in a HITS stimulus pattern file (not to be confused with a HITS model netlist MACRO) defines a sequence of commands, packaged as a unit, which can be called at any point in the process of issuing pattern commands using the APPLY command. A HITS MACRO (and the APPLY commands that implement it) may include arguments, and while the LASAR equivalent SUBROUTINE command (and the equivalent CALL commands that implement it) can also include arguments, a data type must be included for each argument. Because HITS does not include a data type with MACRO arguments, functionality to automatically determine data types was included. This was done by searching the HITS stimulus pattern file for an APPLY command corresponding to each the defined MACRO statements. Once such an APPLY command is found, the arguments passed to the MACRO are stored into a list. Since there are only three different types of arguments allowed in HITS, the detection of the argument type is relatively straightforward. For each argument contained in the list, it is first determined whether it corresponds to a LIST name defined earlier in the program and, if so, the argument is marked as being a GROUP in LASAR. It is then determined whether the argument can be interpreted as an integer value and, if so, it is marked as an INTEGER in LASAR. If neither of the previous conditions is satisfied then the argument is marked as a NODE and the user is given a warning. This is because the NODE type of argument is not valid argument type in LASAR.

Several HITS commands include functionality for specifying a number of patterns over which the command is to be repeated. This functionality is generally translated to LASAR using a simple DO loop. However, the HITS TOGGLE command can produce more complex behavior, and required additional effort to faithfully translate. The TOGGLE

command allows the user to optionally specify the number of patterns over which the TOGGLE command is repeated, the duty cycle (in number of patterns to be maintained) for the toggled state, and the duty cycle for the original state of the specified pin. For each TOGGLE command encountered, including those conjoined by the AND operator, the translator application keeps track of the patterns at which the specified pins will change state based upon the pattern repetition count and the duty cycle parameters. Once all of the TOGGLE commands have been accounted for, whether a single command or multiple conjoined commands, the translator application loops through the list of patterns, determines which pins to toggle, and generates the appropriate equivalent LASAR CHANGE command or commands. In the case that no pins are to change state for a given pattern in the list, a custom subroutine called REPEAT_STIMULUS is called, which reapplies the current stimulus for an additional pattern. In order to reduce the amount of LASAR source data, the translator application determines whether any consecutive patterns toggle exactly the same pins as the current pattern. If so, the translated LASAR CHANGE commands for those pins are enclosed inside a DO loop.

A HITS stimulus pattern file may also include a PATTERNS statement, indicating that the commands that follow belong to a specialized "PATTERNS" section. Within a PATTERNS section, each subsequent line contains only a binary data word (and, perhaps, a comment). The length of the word must be equal to the number of input pins specified in the model netlist, and the word is applied in the same order that the pins are specified. The data word may contain separators, but they must be either dashes (-), equals signs (=), or slashes (/). Otherwise, the data may only be "1", "0", "X", or "Z", setting individual pins to logic high, logic low, "don't care," or high impedance states, respectively. Any other characters are considered invalid and will prompt the end of the PATTERNS section. Patterns that do not contain any instances of "X" or "Z" are translated into standard LASAR DRIVE commands with HITSINPUTS (as described previously) as the pin group operand and any separators removed from the data string. Patterns that contain instances of "X" or "Z" are not currently translated due to complexity and because they are rarely encountered, but future revisions of the translator application may include this functionality. Currently, the user is given a warning and instructed to translate the command manually.

The syntax translated by the convertFaultlist method is almost exclusively HITS PREDETECT commands, although some requisite LASAR syntax is generated, including the "INSERT PRODUCTION FAULTS" command which ensures that all possible faults on all circuit components are considered (and which is implied in HITS faultlist files). Most fault exclusions differ only superficially in syntax between HITS and LASAR, and the automatic translation algorithm is relatively simple. There are three fundamental differences between HITS and LASAR fault exclusions, however.

When faults for an entire component, not merely pins of that component, are excluded in HITS, the prescribed syntax is to enclose the component name in square brackets. In LASAR, the statement EXCLUDE STUCK WITHIN COMPONENT and the component name in angled brackets is equivalent.

Whereas most LASAR component pin fault exclusions occur within a FAULTLIST, initiated with the EXCLUDE FAULTLIST and terminated with the ENDLIST statements, entire-component faults cannot be specified within a FAULTLIST.

Faults may also be excluded for edge pins, and while the syntax for excluding edge pin faults does not differ from the syntax for excluding regular component pin faults in HITS, it does differ in LASAR. For this reason, the edge pins must be retrieved from the HITS model netlist as described earlier to identify edge pins specified in HITS PREDETECT commands and facilitate implementing the LASAR syntax for excluding edge pin faults.

Finally, HITS includes the capability to exclude faults on subcomponent pins. Since these types of faults are not supported in LASAR, the output is appended with a generic warning and a message indicating that the fault was not included in the list for this reason.

B. Implementation and Evaluation

The translator application was implemented using HITS simulation source data from a total of twelve DATSA Test Program Sets (TPSs) that had been rehosted to the L321 ATE, which utilizes LASAR. The reasons for choosing TPSs for which both HITS and LASAR source code already exists are twofold: the existing LASAR simulation provides data against which to judge the efficacy of the translated LASAR simulation, and the availability of custom library circuit components and other information from the existing LASAR simulation simplifies the implementation process.

Literal translation from HITS to LASAR is reasonably possible (either manually, or even automatically, as this paper demonstrates). Yet, none of the LASAR source data for the test article TPSs appears to have been literally translated from the HITS source data. Because both are based upon the same circuit, there is naturally a high degree of commonality between model netlists, but the generated patterns tend to differ greatly between DATSA HITS source data and L321 LASAR source data. It is possible that the HITS simulations were poorly made, but it is also possible that the main reason for redeveloping the simulation is that the requirement for minimum fault coverage could be met using fewer, better-chosen stimulus patterns. This was at a time when processing power was still at a premium and simulation processing could last hours, or even days. Whatever the reason, the difference between the DATSA HITS source data and the L321 LASAR source data presents an opportunity to compare the simulation results of LASAR source data that has been written from scratch with the results of LASAR source data that has been translated directly from HITS source data.

The "CITSCDA6" TPS provided the basis for most of the debugging of the translator application during implementation. Much of the process of implementing this TPS involved amending the syntax that the translator generated until the translated source data compiled in the LASAR environment. However, some of the debugging effort, particularly later in the process after achieving successful compilation, involved attempting to improve the source data in order to achieve a

reasonable fault coverage rate. The remaining eleven TPSs precipitated only debugging efforts necessary to achieve successful LASAR compilation – the translated LASAR source was not amended in an effort to achieve any particular performance threshold. In other words, once the remaining eleven TPSs compiled, their simulation results were left as-is.

After the HITS source data for each TPS was automatically translated into LASAR source data and the LASAR source data was checked against the HITS source data for accuracy, several common instances requiring manual intervention were addressed. The translator application ensures that these instances are always accompanied by a generic warning statement and a message with instructions for performing the manual translation. The formatting of these messages is meant to stand out against the formatting of the surrounding translated source data, so it should be easy for the user to scan the translation and find instances of untranslated code. The effort involved with manually translating untranslated code can vary widely.

In most cases, the circuit component model names from the HITS model netlist were not valid in LASAR due to differences in standard library component names. Therefore, these must be translated manually. Adding functionality for the translator application to perform this step automatically was considered, but it was left to the user’s discretion. This is due to the complexity of programming the automatic translation of circuit component model names (the LASAR system library contains thousands of components), as well as the availability of many very similarly named circuit component models.

Custom circuit components defined using HITS MACRO or FUNCTIONAL commands, and for which exact matches were not found in the local library of the existing LASAR simulation, required developing LASAR custom component definitions so the integrity of the simulation was not compromised. Typical translation efforts will not benefit from the existing LASAR source data, and will therefore require LASAR custom component definitions for all custom HITS components that do not have an equivalent in the LASAR standard library. For the twelve test articles mentioned above, however, most of the circuit components were standard library components in both HITS and LASAR.

After the above instances requiring manual intervention were addressed, the LASAR source data files were transferred to a LASAR workstation. Minor syntax problems and problems arising from non-printing characters that are invalid in the UNIX environment were corrected, and the translated model netlist, stimulus pattern, and faultlist files were compiled for each TPS’s translated LASAR source data. Circuit simulation was performed and fault coverage was “judged” for each. The resulting data was compiled and analyzed. Since alternate TSET specifications were available in the existing LASAR source data, after each translation was simulated and fault coverage was judged, the pattern file was altered to assign each input and output pin to the phase and window, respectively, defined in the TSET of the existing LASAR simulation. For each TPS, the simulation was rerun and the fault coverage again judged. Thus, data for a generic TSET was compared against data for the existing, user-defined TSET.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total test duration was calculated as the product of the simulation clock speed and the pattern count. With one exception, the clock speed utilized in the existing LASAR was less than or equal to the 1 MHz used in the automatically generated, generic timing specification. This reduced clock speed produces a more conservative (i.e. longer) calculation for the total test duration and provides for a more realistic comparison between the durations of the existing and translated LASAR simulations. It is also likely this clock speed represents the maximum clock speed the engineer was able to practically achieve without encountering other issues after transferring the simulation to the ATE environment. For these reasons, the clock speed of the existing LASAR simulations was chosen as the basis for calculating the total test duration of the translated LASAR simulations. The total test duration of the existing LASAR simulations and the translated LASAR simulations for each TPS is presented in graphical form in Fig. 3.

The average test duration among the test article TPSs for existing LASAR simulations was 10.31 ms and for translated LASAR simulations it was 18.26 ms (for the HITS simulations of these TPSs, the average total duration was 26.68 s), which is a difference of 7.95 ms. Discarding two high and low data points, this difference diminishes to less than one millisecond.

The difference in total test duration between the existing and translated LASAR simulations was of particular interest in evaluating the efficacy of the translator application. The performance of the existing LASAR for the test article TPSs was considered to reasonably represent the potential best performance achievable for LASAR simulations generated from scratch. Upon implementing the existing and translated LASAR simulations for the CITSCDA6 TPS, the drastic difference in pattern count (151 for the existing LASAR versus 1034 for the translated LASAR), which resulted in a nearly 600% longer test duration for the translated LASAR, was believed to be typical. Even if such a drastic difference in pattern count had indeed been typical, this drastic difference still only resulted in an absolute difference in test duration of less than one millisecond.

Fig. 3. Total Test Duration – Existing vs. Translated LASAR Simulations

The greatest absolute difference in test duration between existing and translated LASAR, among all of the TPSs, was only slightly above 60 milliseconds. Even if that much of an absolute difference in total test duration were typical, it would require 60,000 test runs to accumulate an hour worth of difference in total time spent running a longer, translated LASAR TPS versus a shorter, from-scratch LASAR TPS. It is unlikely that any DoD TPS experiences such usage over its entire lifetime. Removing outliers from the data set, it appears that a more realistic estimate of the average difference in test duration is less than a millisecond. In fact, the total test duration of the translated LASAR for five of the twelve TPSs actually decreased versus the test duration of the existing LASAR. This evidence suggests that where test duration is concerned, there is no significant benefit from electing to generate a LASAR simulation from scratch. Additionally, a reduced pattern count does not significantly reduce the project engineer's time spent running LASAR simulations on newer, more powerful LASAR workstations.

The fault coverage rate reported by LASAR for each of the test article TPSs, both the existing LASAR simulation and the translated LASAR simulation, is presented in Fig. 4. For this graph, the fault coverage rate value used for the translated LASAR simulation data series is the greater of the translated LASAR fault coverage attained using the generic TSET specifications and the coverage attained using the TSET specifications from the existing LASAR simulation (there was little variation between the two, anyway). The average fault coverage of the existing LASAR simulations is 96%. The average fault coverage of the translated LASAR simulations is 72%. However, if the 3.84% fault coverage achieved by the DEUA19 TPS is removed from consideration, the average fault coverage rate of the translated LASAR simulations increases to 78%. The translated LASAR for four (one out of three) of the test article TPSs achieved a fault coverage of 95% or above; six (one half) achieved a fault coverage of 90% or above; and nine (three quarters) achieved a fault coverage above 60%.

Fig. 4. Fault Coverage Rate – Existing vs. Translated LASAR Simulations

There are numerous possible explanations for the unacceptably low fault coverage attained by the DEUA19 TPS and inadequate fault coverage in other HITS translations. The original HITS simulation may have had inadequate fault coverage to begin with, but because access to the fault coverage rates for HITS simulations was unavailable there is no way to be certain. In fact, it could be that any of the translated LASAR simulations achieves the same fault coverage that its associated HITS translation had achieved. The translated LASAR for the FISCA11 TPS, for example, attained inadequate fault coverage, but the existing LASAR did as well. This would suggest that an inadequate level of fault coverage was accepted, perhaps because the topology of the circuit precludes achieving acceptable fault coverage.

Other possible explanations for inadequate fault coverage include untranslated stimulus commands or fault exclusions, errors in the model netlist (including incorrect node interconnections or component choices), and incorrect TSET specifications (including reliance on slower HITS clock speeds to allow for events like transitions on “one-shot” circuits with long pulse widths). Whatever the reason, the fact is that some translations are not going to immediately meet fault coverage threshold requirements and will require further effort from the assigned project engineer. Four of the twelve test articles, however, achieved the organizationally required fault coverage threshold of 95% without any further effort. Debugging each of the remaining test articles to the point of achieving acceptable fault coverage would be prohibitively time consuming, and was therefore outside the scope of this paper, but it is not unreasonable to expect this extra effort from the project engineer.

The fault coverage initially reported for the translated CITSCDA6 LASAR simulation was 56.26%. However, a minimal additional debugging effort increased the fault coverage to 90.88%. Changing the TSET specifications to match those of the existing LASAR simulation increased it again to 93.84%. None of the other TPSs experienced an increase in fault coverage from similarly changing the TSET specifications. In most cases, changing the TSET information did not affect the fault coverage. In two cases, however, making this change actually worsened the fault coverage rate.

Due to the success of using the TSET specifications from the existing LASAR simulation for the CITSCDA6 TPS, this approach was expected to reliably net an increase in the fault coverage rate. There are several explanations for why it did not, however (although, it is not clear why this change was successful for CITSCDA6). For one, the TSET specifications in the existing LASAR simulation are meant specifically for the patterns as they are generated by existing LASAR, and not meant for the patterns as they were generated by the HITS simulation. In a HITS simulation, the lack of functionality to specify a particular digital format for a pin was overcome with certain, often additional, pattern-generating commands. Also, although the clock speed is much faster than the original HITS simulation, the pattern width is still enough that nodes have ample time to settle. Therefore, the phases and windows specified by the existing LASAR do not make a significant difference versus the generic ones generated automatically by the translator application.

An estimate for the amount of a project engineer's time the translator application stands to save (versus developing a LASAR simulation from scratch) might logically be divided into time spent debugging in an effort to achieve a simulation that compiles and reports fault coverage (debugging time), and time spent making changes to the simulation in an effort to meet the minimum fault coverage requirement (optimization time). The time spent on each of these efforts is dependent upon the engineer's technical ability and familiarity with the circuit.

The tasks involved in debugging time include post-translation code review and error correction, manual translation of standard library component names, manual translation of custom component models (whether they can be replaced with LASAR standard library components or a LASAR custom component definition is required), manual translation of memory device components, manual translation of untranslated pattern-generating commands, amending timing (TSET) specifications, and manual correction of untranslated subroutine arguments. Based upon the effort expended on these tasks for the twelve test article TPSs, and considering those test articles to be representative to HITS simulations in general, the average debugging time was estimated to be 23 hours per TPS.

The optimization time, consisting of the time required to add or modify stimulus patterns to achieve the minimum required fault coverage, is more difficult to estimate. This can represent a significant effort if the fault coverage achieved by a translated simulation is extremely low, but can also represent a minimal effort if the fault coverage of the automatically translated simulation already meets the minimum acceptable level. If the data captured is indicative of translated LASAR simulations in general, then one third of TPSs will require no further optimization effort, one sixth will require minimal optimization effort (perhaps four hours of effort, maximum), one quarter will require moderate optimization effort (perhaps sixteen hours of effort, maximum), and one quarter will require significant optimization effort (perhaps forty hours of effort, maximum). Overall, these estimates combine for an average stimulus pattern optimization time of around 15 hours per TPS. Combined with the estimated debugging time per TPS, the average total estimated time required to develop a working LASAR simulation that meets organizational fault coverage requirements is 38 hours per TPS.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Suggestions for improvements to the translator application include tracking of changes to the HITS textbox (and converting only changed lines in subsequent conversions);

automatic handling of reserved keywords used as variables, pin names, or group names; including the original HITS source data (as comments) alongside the translated LASAR source data; intelligent part recommendations; automatic translation of user-defined component models; and automatically handling "aliases" and pin numbers in HITS edge pin declarations. The feasibility and utility of these enhancements may vary, but the translator application in its current state is already very effective.

This paper presents a new software application that automatically translates source data for the obsolescent digital circuitry simulation and diagnostic assessment platform HITS into source data for LASAR, a similar platform native to modern test equipment. The data presented show that the application is an effective tool and will reduce overall man-hours required for the DATSA to VDATS rehost effort, compared to ground-up development of LASAR source data. Use of the translator application to automatically translate HITS source data into LASAR source data does not pose any significant risk to the rehost effort versus developing LASAR code from scratch. It does not result in a noticeable difference in test duration, and will speed the development of an average LASAR simulation by an estimated 87%, based upon a reduction in simulation development from an historical average of 300 man-hours per TPS (for a complete LASAR simulation development within the 76th Software Maintenance Group) to an estimated 38 man-hours per TPS. The total monetary benefit is an estimated cost savings of \$4.9 million. In conclusion, given the extremely low risk and the appreciable benefit of the translator application, it is clearly an effective tool for the development of LASAR simulations.

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